

SARS-CoV2 Variant and Effect of Therapy

Editorial

Viroj Wiwanitkit*

Professor, Senior Consultant, Public Health Curriculum, SurinRajabhat University, Surin, Thailand.

COVID-19 is an important disease that already causes public health problem around the world. The disease is caused by a new pathogen, SARS - CoV2. At present, the treatment of this disease is still based mainly on supportive and symptomatic treatments. There is still no effective antiviral drug. Although there are many reports on using classic drugs, immunotherapy as well as convalescent plasma therapy for managing COVID-19, all cannot give a favorite outcome.

A difficulty in case management is the fact that the pathogenic virus seems genetic labile. There are many variants and the mutated type can have new properties. The resistance to a drug is probable and it is also a problem in immunotherapy and immunoprevention. The recent report from Hong Kong on the reinfection of COVID-19 in a patient [1] can support the fact that the mutation within the pathogenic virus results in a great difficulty in case management. Basically, a mutation within a molecule can result in molecular weight change and possible structural change. This can result in altered phenotypic expression. This phenomenon is a well explanation on nanopathogenesis of many medical problems [2-5]. Regarding COVID-19, the applied classical antiviral drug against the new virus has to adjust dosage based on the considera-

tion of molecular difference of the old virus and the new SARS - CoV2 [5].

The knowledge on SARS-CoV2 variant is important. Further molecular epidemiology study is required and the in depth nanopathogenesis study on SARS-CoV2 variant is warranted.

References

- [1]. To KK, Hung IF, Ip JD, Chu AW, Chan WM, Tam AR, et al. COVID-19 re-infection by a phylogenetically distinct SARS-coronavirus-2 strain confirmed by whole genome sequencing. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020 Aug 25;ciaa1275. PMID: 32840608.
- [2]. Joob B, Wiwanitkit V. NCF1-339 polymorphism and systemic lupus erythematosus. *Ann Rheum Dis*. 2019 Nov 28; annrheumdis-2019-216629. PMID: 31780525.
- [3]. Sriwijitalai W, Wiwanitkit V. Interleukin-6 -174G/C polymorphism and end-stage renal disease: Is there any role?. *Saudi J Kidney Dis Transpl*. 2018 May-Jun; 29(3): 747-748. PMID: 29970762.
- [4]. Yasri S, Wiwanitkit V. Methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase C677T polymorphism and schizophrenia: Effect of molecular change. *J Res Med Sci*. 2018 Mar 27; 23:20. PMID: 29692817.
- [5]. Yasri S, Wiwanitkit V. Dose prediction of lopinavir/ritonavir for 2019-novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) infection based on mathematic modeling. *Asian Pac J Trop Med*. 2020; 13:137-8.

*Corresponding Author:

Viroj Wiwanitkit,
Professor, Senior Consultant, Public Health Curriculum, SurinRajabhat University, Surin, Thailand.
E-mail: wviroj@yahoo.com

Received: August 28, 2020

Published: August 31, 2020

Citation: Viroj Wiwanitkit. SARS-CoV2 Variant and Effect of Therapy. *Int J Chronic Dis Ther*. 2020;6(1e):1. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.19070/2332-2926-200009e>

Copyright: Viroj Wiwanitkit® 2020. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.